

DIMENSIONS OF SOCIAL EXCLUSION IN THE INSTITUTIONAL, EDUCATIONAL AND PSYCHOSOCIAL ASPECTS OF VISUALLY IMPAIRED INDIVIDUALS

Zeynep Arik¹,

Deniz Ozcan²

¹Special Education Department,
Faculty of Education,
Near East University,
North Cyprus

²Special Education Department,
Faculty of Education,
Ondokuz Mayıs University,
Turkey

Abstract:

This research was carried out to determine the dimensions of social exclusion in the institutional, economic and psychosocial aspects of visually impaired individuals. This research, which was designed in mixed research method, was done by using descriptive survey design. In the framework of the study, the study group consists of 30 visually impaired individuals who are active members of the Turkish Cypriot Visually Impaired Individuals Association in Nicosia. As a data collection tool, a semi-structured interview form consisting of 32 questions, open and closed ends, was used to examine the lives of the visually impaired. The quantitative data obtained are presented quantitatively by using SPSS (statistical program for social sciences). Content analysis was used for qualitative data. It has been concluded that people with visual disabilities have been excluded from the physical environment, employment, education and health areas and psychosocial aspects due to the negative attitudes of the media and society towards the disabled.

Keywords: visually impaired individuals, social exclusion, exclusion

1. Introduction

According to the Cyprus Turkish Orthopedic Disability Association, the number of people with disabilities in TRNC is about 5 thousand and 188 persons. This figure is increasing every day (KTOÖD, 2016). However, this figure also includes cancer patients, dialysis patients and individuals with certain chronic diseases. Although disability is not a disease, it can be put in the same category. With the exception of

diseases, individuals with life-long deprivation are around 4,500. 409 of these individuals are visually impaired. The visually impaired individuals take very little space in social life, so there are more visually impaired individuals than expected. Every day, the number of people with disabilities increases and this brings along social, institutional and economic exclusion (Akbulut, 2012; Appleton & Field, 2014; Arslan and others, 2014; Aslan & Seker, 2011). For a disabled individual, one of the most important things is independence. The biggest obstacles to independence are in the areas of access to physical environment and services. Accessibility of community environments and availability of transportation options are key to the exclusion dimension in the physical environment (Appleton, 2014).

While designing a communal space in TRNC; no matter indoor / outdoor structures and arrangements in public spaces, design is made for individuals who develop normally. This is the exclusion of the disabled individuals shown to us and this is also exclusion from the physical environment. Especially in the last 5 years, ramps or yellow lines started to be built for visually impaired people or people with disabilities, but these can sometimes be showy. For example, in Kumsal Park in Nicosia, yellow-lined roads were added for visually impaired individuals. However, these yellow stripes were constructed according to the designs in 1999. The current white walking sticks do not fit these measures (Suay, 2018).

Visually impaired people have more risks such as falls and injuries (Arslan and others, 2014; Bonner, 2008). Sidewalks and roads in the TRNC are not intended to be used by a visually impaired person. It is not possible for them to come out without a companion. The sidewalks, which even an individual has trouble using it, have become ideal places for car parks. This is one of the biggest obstacles to independence. Visually impaired individuals live in four walls; they are socially excluded from the physical environment. The fact that the disabled individuals with 10% of the population are not able to use their physical and mental abilities and skills other than obstacles should not be seen as a burden on the national economy, but as lost economic values for every society. With a good regulation, if disabled people are employed in suitable jobs, it is possible to benefit from disabled labor as much as individuals without disabilities (Baykoc, 2014).

Employment problems have been significantly reduced with vocational training programs in modern countries. In addition to basic education in the UK, vocational education provides for individuals with disabilities. Not only did it provide work, but the process was strengthened after having the profession with the necessary controls and works. In Japan, the majority of visually impaired people are trained in the Japanese traditional massage technique, finger massage and acupuncture (Dernekbas, 2010).

There is a Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities in the TRNC. In article 4 of article 6 of Law No 64/93, it is clearly stated that 1 out of every 25 people in the workplace is disabled individuals. However, this law is openly exploited. The law itself is also discriminatory and existing provisions are not applied. Persons with

disabilities are not counted as public officials even if they are employed in the public sector and they have no chance of promotion. However, an unimpeded individual who does the same work has a chance to be promoted. Again, a disabled individual has to wait for retirement in order to receive severance pay. It is also evident that disabled individuals may face social exclusion in terms of employment (Polili, 2012).

Günay Kibrit, the President of the Cyprus Turkish Orthopedic Disability Association said that since 2006, not a single disabled person has been employed (Havadis, 2018). Some visually impaired individuals complete their education under difficult conditions but they may not find a job for their conditions. (Polili, 2012) Some individuals with disabilities may choose not to work, even if they can work, in order not to lose their salary. Visually impaired individuals in the TRNC are socially excluded from employment.

Access barriers can lead to complex and interconnected consequences, such as increased physical and mental health problems or economic distress. Equal access to health services is an urgent matter. Physical health and worsening economic, social and psychological health can be the results of access barriers that prevent or delay patients from receiving health services. (Neri & Kroll, 2003)

Lack of education is one of the main factors leading to social exclusion and poverty. Children with disabilities have often limited access to mainstream education. Both ECHP (Eurostat) data and the low level of access to education for children with disabilities are noteworthy. (Yfantopoulos, 2002)

The main problem of disabled people is education. The lack of education of disabled individuals is one of the most important problems facing the integration of the society. Education is very important to expand the life expectancy of people with disabilities, as for any other group. In addition, socialization of children with disabilities plays an important role in societies with social exclusion of people with disabilities. Despite its importance, educational outcomes for disabled children and adults remain very weak. (Ozturk, 2011)

1.2 Purpose of the Study

The aim of this study was to determine the socio-demographic characteristics of visually impaired individuals in TRNC; to determine the dimensions of social exclusion in the institutional, economic and psychosocial terms. For this purpose, the following questions will be sought.

1. What are the socio-demographic characteristics of visually impaired individuals in TRNC?
2. What is the extent of the social exclusion of visually impaired individuals in terms of institutional and economic aspects?
 - 2.1. What is the extent of social exclusion in which visually impaired individuals live in terms of physical environmental conditions?
 - 2.2. What is the extent of social exclusion for visually impaired individuals in terms of employment?

- 2.3. What is the extent of social exclusion experienced by visually impaired individuals in terms of education?
- 2.4. What is the extent of social exclusion for visually impaired individuals in terms of health?
3. What is the extent of the social exclusion of the visually impaired individuals from the psychosocial perspective?
 - 3.1. What is the extent of social exclusion for the visually impaired individuals in terms of the media?
 - 3.2. What is the extent of social exclusion for visually impaired individuals in terms of society?

2. Method

2.1. Research Model

In this study, a mixed research model was used to examine the dimensions of social exclusion in the institutional, economic and psychosocial aspects of visually impaired individuals. Mixed research method is a research method that uses both quantitative and qualitative questions and combines these two sets of data. (Creswell, 2017)

2.2. Study Group

The population of the study is visually impaired individuals, with the exception of hearing, physical and speech impaired individuals. The sample of the study is the visually impaired individuals who are active members of the Turkish Cypriot visually impaired Association in Nicosia.

After negotiations with the Association, a list of members who are active was obtained. Within the scope of the study, 7 people from the Magusa region, 6 people from the Güzelyurt region, 10 people from the Nicosia region and 7 people from the Kyrenia region were interviewed. A total of 30 visually impaired individuals were reached and interviewed.

2.3. Data collection tool

The interview form developed by the researchers was used as data collection tool. The interview is an oral communication between at least two people. Interviewing can be expressed as, collecting data from related persons within the framework of the questions sought in the research. (Buyukozturk et al., 2016) In this study, semi-structured interview was used. This data collection tool was preferred in order to reach both fixed choice and depth in the related field.

In this study, researcher consulted one linguist and one survey evaluator in the field to examine the experiences of the visually impaired people who are active members of the Turkish Cypriot Visually Impaired Association in Nicosia. A semi-structured interview form was prepared and finalized according to expert opinions.

The semi-structured interview form used in the study consists of 32 questions. Questions are about personal and disability information in order to understand the demographic characteristics of people with disabilities, questions about their everyday life in order to learn the physical environmental conditions and difficulties, questions about employment, education, health services and the difficulties faced by them, how the media perceived the disabled people, social ideas for disabled people and how these thoughts make people feel who are visually impaired.

2.4. Data Analysis

Within the scope of the study, data were collected by using SPSS (Statistical Program for Social Sciences) Version 23.0 program for quantitative data collected from 30 visually impaired individuals and submitted quantitatively. Percentage and frequency were used to analyze the data. Content analysis was used for qualitative data. According to the data collected by the researcher, the coding process was performed. The codes were then combined and categorized according to their common point. At this stage, the quotations are given frequently in order to understand the data clearly. The validity and reliability of the data are obtained in detail how to reach the results. The views of visually impaired individuals are frequently quoted. For reliability, the researcher avoided directing the participants, only asked the questions of the researcher. Of the 30 papers, 15 were randomly selected and individually assessed by another researcher. Consistency was found to be 80%.

3. Results

3.1. Features of the participants related to their personal characteristics and barriers

In this section, the visually impaired participants will be introduced in terms of their characteristics features related to barriers.

Table 1: Gender of visually impaired individuals who participated in the study

Gender	N	%
Woman	10	33.3
Man	20	66.7
Total	30	100.0

As seen in Table 1, 66.7% (20 people) of the participants were male participants and 33.3% (10 persons) were female participants.

Table 2: The ages of visually impaired individuals who participated in the study

Age	N	%
18-30	7	23.3
31-40	3	10.0
41-50	4	13.3
51-60	4	13.3

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61-70	11	36.7
71 and above	1	3.3
Total	30	100.0

23.3% of the visually impaired individuals (7 persons) were in the 18-30 age group, 10% were in the 31-40 (3 person) age range, 13.3% (4 persons) in the 41-50 age range, 13.3% were in the age range of 51-60 (4 people), 36.7% were in the 61-70 age range, while 3.3% (1 person) were in the 71 and upper years.

Table 3: Birth places of visually impaired individuals who participated in the research

Birth Places	N	%
Nicosia	7	23.3
Kyrenia	4	13.3
Lefka	1	3.3
Larnaca	3	10.0
Limasol	1	3.3
Famagusta	7	23.3
Other	7	23.3
Total	30	100.0

As shown in Table 3, 23.3% (7 people) of the participants were in Nicosia, 13.3% (4 persons) in Kyrenia, 3.3% (1 person) in Lefka, 10% (3 persons) in Larnaca, 3.3% (one person) in Limassol, 23.3% (7 persons) in Famagusta, 23.3% (7 persons) participants are moved to the TRNC after born in Turkey's different provinces. After the events of 1963, the participants migrated from Larnaca and Limasol in the southern part and settled in the northern provinces.

Table 4: Marital status of visually impaired individuals who participated in the study

Marital Status	N	%
Single	10	33.3
Married	19	63.3
Other	1	3.3
Total	30	100.0

Table 4 shows the marital status of visually impaired individuals participating in the study. While 33.3% (10 people) were single, 63.3% (19 people) were married. 3.3% (1 person) participating in the study is the other option. Alternatively, the other part of the study was added to avoid the feeling of being interfered with in the private life of visually impaired individuals. As seen in Table 4, it is understood that most of the participants were married.

Table 5: Having children situation for visually impaired individuals who have participated in the research

Child	N	%
Yes	20	66.7
No	10	33.3
Total	30	100.0

While 66.7% of the visually impaired individuals (20 people) had children, 33.3% (10 persons) had no children. It is understood that all the married individuals who participated in the study had children.

Table 6: Distribution of visually impaired individuals according to the number of children

Number of Children	N	%
1 child	4	20.0
2 children	12	60.0
3 children	4	20.0
Total	20	100.0

20% of the participants (4 people) have 1 child, 60% (12 persons) have 2 children and the remaining 20% (4 persons) have 3 children. As can be seen in Table 6, the survey participants are married and the majority of the others have 2 children.

In the following tables, the characteristics of visually impaired individuals who participated in the research will be discussed.

Table 7: The level of disability of visually impaired individuals who participated in the research

The Level of Disability	N	%
Sightless	11	36.7
Low Vision	16	53.3
Monocular	3	10.0
Total	30	100.0

As seen in Table 7, 36.7% of the visually impaired individuals (11 people) who do not see at all, 53.3% (16 people) are low vision and 10% (3 persons) are monocular. Monocular vision is only in the case of visual impairment in which an eye is affected. As it can be understood from Table 7, the low vision disability group is majority and the individuals affected by monocular ignorance constitute the minority.

Table 8: Use of vehicle support by visually impaired individuals who participated in the study

Vehicle Support	N	%
Yes	7	23.3
No	23	76.7
Total	30	100.0

As seen in Table 8, 23.3% (7 persons) of the visually impaired people received vehicle support and 76.7% of them did not have vehicle support. Used vehicle supports include white walking sticks and smart watches. Although most of the participants stated that they requested assistance from the association, no support was provided by the association.

Table 9: The disability reason for visually impaired individuals who participated in the research

Disability Reason	N	%
Prenatal causes	10	33.3
During delivery of birth causes	3	10.0
Postnatal causes	17	56.7
Total	30	100.0

As it is understood from Table 9, 33.3% (10 people) of the visually impaired individuals who participated in the study were born congenitally, 10% (3 persons) were born during delivery, and the remaining 56.7% (17 persons) were visually impaired for postnatal reasons. The following tables will explain the reasons for prenatal, during delivery of birth and postnatal reasons.

Table 10: Prenatal causes of congenital visually impaired individuals who participated in the research

Prenatal Causes	N	%
Consanguineous Marriage	5	50.0
Hereditary Diseases	1	10.0
Mother's Disease	2	20.0
Cause Unknown	2	20.0
Total	10	100.0

Of the 30 visually impaired individuals 10 (33.3%) were visually impaired because of prenatal, and half of these 10 people (5 people) were visually impaired because of consanguineous marriage, 10% (1 person) of hereditary diseases, 20% (2 people) of mother's diseases during the pregnancy and the remaining 20% (2 people) did not know the cause of visual impairment

As it is understood from Table 10, consanguineous marriages were the cause for half of the visually impaired individuals who participated in the study who were affected from prenatal reasons.

Table 11: Causes of during delivery of birth for visually impaired individuals who participated in the research

Causes of During Delivery of Birth	N	%
Poor childbirth	2	66.7
Implementation by insufficient staff	1	33.3
Total	3	100.0

As shown in Table 11, a total of 3 people were visually impaired due to causes of during delivery of birth reasons while 66.7% (2 people) of 3 people were affected by the fact that the birth occurred in bad conditions and 33.3% (1 person) was affected by implementation of birth by insufficient staff.

Table 12: The causes of postnatal causes of visually impaired individuals who participated in the research

Postnatal Causes	N	%
Diseases	7	41.2
Accidents	8	47.0
Wrong Treatments	2	11.8
Total	17	100.0

Of the 30 visually impaired individuals, 17 were visually impaired after birth. Of these 17 patients, 41.2% (7 people) because of the result of diseases, 47% (8 people) as a result of various accidents and 11.8% (2 people) were visually impaired due to wrong treatment.

Table 13: Age of visually impaired individuals-after birth causes who participated in the study

Age of Visual Impairment after Birth	N	%
0-6	3	17.8
7-15	6	35.3
16-30	5	29.4
31 and over	3	17.5
Total	17	100.0

In total, 17 of the 30 disabled individuals who participated in the study had a visual impairment after birth. 17.8% (3 persons) of 17 people were visually impaired in the 0-6 age range, 35.3% (6 persons) in the 7-15 age range, 29.4% (5 persons) in the 16-30 age range and the remaining 17.5% (3 people) had visual impairment at the age of 31 years and over. As it can be understood from the table, it can be concluded that individuals who have visual impairment had their disability at a young age.

The following tables will focus on the institutional and economic exclusion status of visually impaired individuals.

3.2. Findings on Social Exclusion Situation of Institutional and Economic Exclusion Status for Visually Impaired Individuals.

Table 14: The occupation of visually impaired individuals

Theme	Subcodes	f
Occupation	Student	3
	Retired	10
	Housewife	4
	Unemployed	9
	Agricultural technician	1
	Software Developer	1
	Self-Employment	1

When we look at Table 14, 3 of the visually impaired individuals are students, 10 of them are retired, 4 of them are housewives, 1 of them are agricultural technicians, 1 person is a software developer, 1 person is self-employed while 9 people do not do any work. When we look at the table, it can be seen that approximately 3/1 of the visually impaired individuals are not engaged in any job. The other 3/1 is retired, while the remaining 3/1 consists of housewives, students and individuals who are already engaged in a job.

Table 15: The way of finding a job for visually impaired individuals

The Way of Finding a Job	N	%
Self	11	61.1
Friend	3	16.6
Family	1	5.7
Disabled quota	3	16.6
Total	18	100.0

Of the 30 visually impaired individuals who participated in the study, 9 were unemployed and 3 were students. Of the remaining 18 persons, 61.1% (11 persons) were self-employed, 16.6% (3 persons) found a job with the help of a friend and 5.7% (1 person) found a job with the help of a family of and only 16.6% (3 persons) found a job through with the disability quota.

Table 16: Factors affecting the work life of visually impaired individuals who participated in the research

Work Life	N	%
Physical environment conditions	6	15.8
Inadequate training due to disability	1	2.6
Negative working conditions	6	15.8
Lack of profession	5	13.4
Due to Disability	10	26.2
Negative attitudes of employers due to disability	0	0.00
None	10	26.2
Total	*38	100.0

The distribution of the visually impaired individuals according to the factors affecting their work life is examined in 6 categories. These categories are defined as physical

environment conditions at work, lack of education due to disability, negative working conditions, lack of profession, disability and negative attitudes of employers. According to these categories, 15.8% (6 people) of the visually impaired individuals participated in the study stated that the problem is the physical environment conditions. (5 people) stated that there was no occupation, 2.6% (1 person) stated that the problem lack of education, 26.2% (10 people) were the factors affecting work life due to the disability. Due to the disability of the visually impaired individuals participating in the research, it was observed that employers were not affected by the negative attitude factor. It was understood that the individuals who had started their work life before the visually impaired disability did not have any factors affecting their work life. According to this, 26.2% (10 people) stated that there were no factors affecting work life. As there are 6 categories in the factors affecting the work life, the visually impaired individuals answered the question according to their priorities. They did not respond to some categories. In general, it was observed that the individuals who participated in the study had a disability; negative working conditions according to their disability or negatively affected the physical environment conditions at workplaces. Participants on this subject stated that:

“Business environments are full of physical barriers. For example, the width of corridors, toilets, ramps are not suitable for us. All of these must be built according to disabled people, in public or private sector. The room while we were a room in the warehouse. When I was going to the room, I’d knock over boxes and books. I’d knock over exclusively so that they could understand their mistakes. You gave a room like this to a disabled person you deserve this kind of behaviour.” (K2)

“Not being a social state is an obstacle. Necessary measures should be taken in the workplace for a visually impaired person. The social state is the state that takes all necessary measures to deal with all citizens without disabilities.” (K15)

“...working conditions are not for me. There is no environment and understanding where a disabled person can work.” (K27)

“There’s no work for me. No equal conditions.” (K28)

Such opinions have been reported. While visually impaired individuals are excluded from work life due to their disability, they are excluded because of negative working conditions and lack of physical environment conditions.

Table 17: Situation of earn a living for the family of visually impaired individuals who participated in the research

Earn a living for the family	N	%
Parents	7	23.3
Parents-Disability salary	1	3.3
Partner-Disability salary	12	40.3
Self	7	23.3
Disability Salary	3	10.0
Total	30	100.0

When looking at the person or persons who provided the livelihood of the house, 23.3% of the visually impaired individuals (7 people) were parents, 3.3% (1 person) parents and their own disability salary and 40.3% (12 persons) parents and their own disability salary ,23.3% on their own, and the remaining 10% (3 persons) only provide with their disability salary.

Table 18: The adequacy of the income obtained by the visually impaired individuals who participated in the research

The Adequacy of the Income	N	%
Adequate	18	60.0
Inadequate	12	40.0
Total	30	100.0

Looking at Table 18, it can be seen that 60% of the visually impaired individuals (18 people) are sufficient to meet the basic requirements of the income they earn, and the remaining 40% (12 people) is not sufficient for the basic requirements.

Table 19: The negativity of the working environment for visually impaired individuals who participated in the study

Theme	Subcodes	f
Negativity of the working environment	Lack of equal work environment	6
	Lack of negative impact	6
	Falling injury, wounding	2
	Being a student	3
	Disability salary	2
	No quota	2
	Increased of disability level	9

According to Table 19, 6 people of the disabled people who participated in the study were negatively affected by the absence of equal work environment, 2 people were affected by accidents such as falling, injury, etc., 2 people stay away from business life to avoid to lose disability salary, 6 people due to not open the quota, 9 people stated that they could not work because the their disability level increases. As the remaining 3 people were students, they did not experience the negative side of business life. and 4 people stated that they did not experience the negativity of the business life, preferably because they were housewives.

In general, individuals with disabilities who have participated in the research have either left their jobs or have retired early due to an increase in the level of disability. The absence of equal environment and quota were reflected negatively in the work life. Participants expressed their opinions as follows:

"When I was working, my eyes went even worse because I got infected while I was doing work. So I can't work at all now." (K21)

"Due to the disability I could not continue my working life. I was slog on and had to leave." (K11)

"My level of disability increased while working. I had to quit my job if I didn't want to." (K13)

"I started as a driver, but when my eyes progressed, I quit. I've seen negative attitudes from some people. I was upset that they said I was paid unjustly." (K16)

"I can't find a job. Disabled quota is not opened. I have no more hope. There is no improvement for years." (K29)

"I can't work because there is no quota. The quota for us does not open for 10 years." (K8)

"I became unable to work after being disabled. The Association helped me and I was able to retire early." (K22)

"I used to work before, but I had to quit after my eyes. I couldn't work. I can't find another job for my disability. For a person who cannot see is almost impossible to find work on this island. How many years did not open the quota. Maybe we could use that if it was open. Did I not want to work like everyone else? To earn my own money?" (K30)

In general, the visually impaired individuals were unemployed at a rate of 3/1, the visually impaired individuals were not sufficiently utilized, and the visually impaired individuals could not benefit from the disability quota, the disability salary is not sufficient for living independently, the absence of equal work environment, the design of workplaces and environments without thinking disabled people; it can be said that there is an exclusion of visually impaired individuals in terms of economic and employment status.

The following tables will focus on the exclusion status of visually impaired individuals in terms of education.

Table 20: Distribution of visually impaired individuals
 according to their educational status

Education Status	N	%
Illiterate	2	6.7
Primary school graduate	7	23.3
Secondary school graduate	10	33.3
High school graduate	6	20.0
Graduated from a University	4	13.3
Master	1	3.3
Total	30	100.0

As shown in Table 20, 6.7% (2 persons) of the 30 disabled individuals who participated in the study were illiterate; one of these people did not start the education institution and the other one started primary school but stopped reading because of health problems, and 23.3% (7 people) of primary school graduates, 33.3% (10 people) secondary school graduates, 20% (6 people) graduated from high school, 13.3% (4 people) university graduate and the remaining 3.3% (1 person) is a master.

In general, it is understood that the majority are middle school or high school graduates. Based on this, it can be said that the degree of education among the visually impaired individuals is average. They mostly left the school. As a reason, it is possible to state that they have difficulty in education, lack of appropriate educational environment, lack of support and support by peers. These reasons will be explained in more detail in Table 23.

Table 21: The type of school for visually impaired individuals
 who attended the research

Type of School	N	%
General education institution	26	87.7
Special education institution	3	10.0
No education	1	3.3
Total	30	100.0

As indicated in Table 21, 87.7% of the visually impaired individuals (26 persons) attending the study went to general education institution, 10% went to special education institution and the remaining 3.3% (1 person) did not go to school.

The majority have received training in the general education institution. On the increase level of visually impairment, most of them had to leave half-way. There was no separate school for the visually impaired at the time most participants went to school. These students were directed either to the general education institution or to the mixed special education institution. Those who were referred to private education institutions preferred to go to general education. One of the visually impaired participants stated the situation as follows:

“I started special education before. But all the disability groups were in one class. Biting, attacking kids, and I scared. I could not focus on the lessons from my fear. While they did

not understand the lessons, I could understand, but I just couldn't see. I was fall behind. So I went to the general education institution. I had a hard time reading books." (K8)

Rauf Raif Denktas Visually Impaired Special Education School which has been giving education since 2002-2003 continues to provide education. But there are only 2 teachers in the school. And this is not a sufficient number. This school is also located in Nicosia only. Those who have difficulty in transportation may not choose to send their children to this school. There is no condition of providing any service to the school.

Table 22: Factors affecting the educational life of visually impaired individuals participating in the research

Educational Life	Yes		No		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
I was not having difficulty accessing the education institution.	8	30.8	18	70.2	26	100.0
Building structures and arrangements were enough	8	30.8	18	70.2	26	100.0
I didn't need additional support in the classroom	12	46.1	14	54.9	26	100.0
Teachers' attitudes were positive	17	65.3	9	34.7	26	100.0
I was supported by my peers	13	50.0	13	50.0	26	100.0
I wasn't experiencing financial difficulties	8	30.8	18	70.2	26	100.0
I participated in school activities	16	61.5	10	38.5	26	100.0

Factors affecting educational experience were examined in 7 categories. These categories have been identified as the difficulty of accessing the educational institution, the adequacy of the internal structure and regulations of buildings, the need for support and support in the classroom, the attitudes of teachers, peer support, financial difficulties and participation in school activities.

While there are 30 visually impaired participants in the study, 26 people represented for the factors affecting the educational life. The reason for this is that 1 person has never started his education life, he has not had any experience with any educational institution, 1 person has started school and left school at the beginning and he has not answered the questions about this subject. The remaining two people had visual impairment after their education and did not experience any difficulties in the education life.

In addition, 70.2% (18 persons) of the remaining 26 persons had difficulties in accessing the educational institution and 70.2% (18 people) stated that they were inadequate according to the obstacles of the internal and external regulations in the educational institutions. 54.9% (14 people) needed additional support and assistance within the classroom. The further the degree of disability, the more support and assistance needed. 65.3% (17 people) were found to be positive attitudes for teachers. While 50% (13 people) had the support of their peers, the remaining 50% did not have peer support. 70.2% (18 people) experienced financial problems during their education. 61.5% (16 people) had no problems attending school activities.

In general, more than most of the participants were affected by the factors affecting their education life; it experienced difficulties in transportation to schools, financial situation and physical arrangements of buildings.

Table 23: The factors affecting the education life of visually impaired individuals

Theme	Subcodes	f
Factors Affecting Education	Year loss	2
	Unable to read books	8
	Easing in school	6
	Exclusion	4
	Lack of appropriate training	14
	Being visually impaired after education	3
	1963 events and after	3
	Other	3

When we look at Table 23, 2 people have had problems related to the loss of the year. Participants expressed the opinion as follows:

"I had no difficulty. But he was not given a diploma in elementary school. I had to finish outside and lost 2 years. And transportation was very distressing." (K1)

"The forms of exams were forcing me. We don't have a test system. The oral examinations in the TRNC did not count. That's why I lost 2 years." (K2)

8 people stated that they have difficulty writing, reading books, blackboard and notebooks.

"I was tired early because of my eyes. I was having trouble using a microscope when I was in high school. I was having trouble reading books" (K4)

"I couldn't read books. I couldn't see the questions in the exams. I needed help." (K24)

6 people mocked at school and 4 people stated that they were excluded from school.

"They mocked at school. I couldn't read the articles, they were mocking and I didn't go to school again." (K6)

"I was being teased by my friends." (K10)

"I was being teased by my friends." (K11)

"I was being teased. I couldn't wear glasses. Because they were mocking. I've been able to hold up to middle school. Then I continued special education." (K14)

"I've had the problem of adapting. There were teasing and disdain. I was able to make friends difficultly." (K21)

"I had a hard time reading. From time to time I was mocking by my peers. I'd love to go to college, but I scared. I've done it this way until high school, but the college is different. You need to be more independent there." (K29)

14 people were affected by the lack of suitable educational facilities for the visually impaired.

"I had to stop reading after my eyes because I didn't have a school to go." (K30)

"Reading books, going to school, lack of guidance and service was very difficult. I broke 10 glasses until I settled down inside the building (school)." (K2)

"I could not continue my education due to my eyes." (K16)

"I was able to manage because I was visually impaired after education life, but it was very hard to finish school. Exams, books, school order were not according to a visually impaired person." (K28)

"I was sweating because of my eyes and I was suffering from a headache. That's why I couldn't focus on classes." (K20)

After the education life, 3 people had visual disability. 3 people were affected by the 1963 events and 3 people stated that there were other problems.

"I left school because I was sick of epilepsy." (K5)

"I didn't have any problems in education because I was visually impaired after education life." (K6)

"I had to leave my education halfway because of the 1963 events" (K13)

"Since I was visually impaired after education life, I didn't have much difficulty in my education life. I wanted to continue my education life, but my father wanted me to support the home so I began to work." (K22)

"I could not continue my education due to the difficulties of transportation and the difficulties of the war period." (K19)

More than half of the visually impaired individuals participated in the research had problems with transportation to school, to adapt to the internal structures of buildings and regulations, educational environment, ridiculed and excluded by their peers and financial problems. Accordingly, it can be said that the inclusion of visually impaired individuals in the education system is prevented. The education system has gone into a structured without thinking disabled individuals. According to this, it can be said that visually impaired people are excluded from education.

The following tables will focus on the exclusion status of people with disabilities in the health sector.

Table 24: The opinions of visually impaired individuals about health services

Health Services	Yes		No		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
I have no difficulty in accessing for health services	8	26.7	22	73.3	30	100.0
I am satisfied with the examinations in health institutions	13	43.3	17	56.7	30	100.0
Health professionals treats good	19	63.3	11	36.7	30	100.0
I can speak freely with health professionals	20	66.7	10	33.3	30	100.0
I don't need personal help	12	40.0	18	60.0	30	100.0

In Table 24, 5 categories were presented to learn the opinions of visually impaired individuals about health services. These categories are defined as access to health services, satisfaction in the practice, health professionals' behavior and communication styles, and finally, personal assistance needs. Of the 30 visually impaired individuals, 73.3% (22 people) had difficulty accessing health services. 56.7% (17 people) are not satisfied with the practice in health institutions.

63.3% (19 people) think that health professionals are well behaved and 66.7% (20 people) can speak to each subject with health experts. In the last category, 60% (18 persons) of the visually impaired individuals need personal assistance in health institutions.

Table 25: The negativities sides of health services for visually impaired individuals

Theme	Subcodes	f
Health care challenges	No Challenges	4
	Falls, bruising in hospitals	4
	Drug shortage	4
	Failure of operations	2
	Appointment system	1
	Malpractice	5
	Lack of psychological support	7
	State-Private hospitals	2

4 people of 30 visually impaired individuals who participated in the study stated that they did not have any difficulties regarding health services. The difficulties experienced according to the degree of visual impairment can vary. Participants stated that they were able to manage according to the level of sight obstacle and reported that they did

not experience any difficulties. 5 people have previously been afraid of falling down in the hospital or bruising.

"When I went to the hospital I fell a lot. They were not interested. I used the service of the municipality, but I'm sorry, they take me away like a kitten to the hospital. You have to do everything yourself. But I can't see where I'm going. I'm doing my own work in the house, but I'm when I am out it is very difficult for me." (K3)

"I need a companion when I go to the hospital. It's hard for me to climb the stairs. I'm afraid of falling." (K25)

"Transportation is very difficult for me. I need help when I get there. How many times I was in danger of falling down the stairs." (K30)

Of the 30 visually impaired individuals participating in the study, 4 people stated that they were experiencing difficulties in providing medication shortages. 2 people said they cannot meet the problems of their own facilities, 1 person stated that appointment system did not perform; 5 people reported that they had lost one or both eyesight due to wrong treatment, 7 people had problem about lacked psychological support, and 2 people had not got attention in state hospitals and that they could not go to a private hospital.

"The board did not accept my surgery here. I went on my own to Turkey. I lost my eye in the army. This surgery had to be met. If they took me properly to the army, they had to take care of me or at least support me." (K4)

"I can't take my medication. There is no support in this regard. There's a shortage of drugs. I can't always find my medication. And I completely lost an eye on the wrong treatment." (K5)

"There is no interest. We're nothing. They are going over us. Everything is not money. If I go to his clinic, he's not going to act like this. But I can't give money to the private hospital. I don't have that. They have to take care of me, but they don't. The appointment system doesn't work. We can't find a doctor when we're gone, and we're going to have to go back to home." (K9)

"I'm having trouble with the drug; I'm having difficulty accessing it. The drugs I use are very expensive and the salary I receive is not enough." (K11)

"I didn't have a chance for surgery because the doctors here are unconscious." (K12)

“I didn’t need surgery, but they did the surgery. That’s why I completely lost my eye.”
 (K13)

“I lost my eyes from the wrong treatment and medications. They don’t care if you don’t go to a private clinic. The association needs to check the risky patients. In KKTC, especially patients need psychological support.” (K16)

“I completely lost the eye because of the wrong treatment. I went to Turkey, but we paid for everything.” (K17)

“There is both unconsciousness and apathy in health services. Everything is harder if these are together.” (K18)

“General state hospitals very distressed, I go to private hospital.” (K19)

“The operations here have always gone wrong. I had an infection and I completely lost an eye. I needed psychological support after the surgery, but no one has given such support. My doctor told me I lost my eye, and he left. I’ve faced this reality in the room. They didn’t even let my mother into the room.” (K21)

“I’m having a lot of trouble getting drugs. Sometimes I can’t find the drugs I should use. Or there are very expensive ones and the salary is not enough.” (K24)

In general, 3/2 of the visually impaired individuals in the study have difficulties in transportation in the health sector and they need personal assistance and support, they are not satisfied with the practices in health institutions. It can be said that physical facilities of health institutions are not suitable for visually impaired individuals, and buildings such as stairs and roads inside and outside the building make it more difficult for visually impaired individuals. Persons with visual disabilities who could not afford to undergo surgery, there are lots of wrong treatments, shortage of medicines, they could not find psychological support after these operations. For these reasons, it can be said that visually impaired individuals face unconsciousness and apathy in the health sector.

In the following tables, the exclusion status of the visually impaired individuals in the physical environment will be discussed.

Table 26: Difficulties of the visually impaired individuals in the physical environment

Theme	Subcodes	f
Difficulties in the Physical Environment	Independence	14
	Obstacles on the Sidewalk	10
	Signaling	3
	Inability of yellow lined roads	3
	Insufficient infrastructure	4
	Pits	6

The visually impaired individuals stated that they could not move independently in the physical environment in relation to the difficulties in the physical environment. They said they had to go out with someone.

"I can't walk without anyone, I can't go out. There is no freedom for us on the island." (K1)

"I'm having all kinds of difficulties. There is great distress in the independent movement for a visually impaired." (K2)

"I can't go anywhere alone. I get help. I can't go to a store. I can't cross the street. I can only go to one of two places very close to the neighborhood." (K3)

"I don't go out much anymore. I'm living in the house. My wife and children help if I want something." (K11)

"I can't get out if I don't have to. I've already locked myself in. It's not like I'm coming out. I can't even go to the bank." (K13)

"If I cannot act independently, this is the problem of society." (K15)

While 10 of the visually impaired individuals expressed their opinions about the obstacles on the side-walks, 3 people expressed lack of signaling and 3 persons expressed the inadequacy of the yellow-lined roads

4 people highlighted the lack of infrastructure for the visually impaired, while 6 people mentioned the danger of potholes on the side-walks and roads.

"We have sidewalks that even healthy people cannot heart. There are all kinds of obstacles. A visually impaired has no chance to walk alone on our sidewalks. Pedestrian crossings no lift signaling. There is only one in one place, it does not work well. Even the steps here are not standard. Two times I was in danger of falling. I had my guide dog. He had 2 near death experience. So I had to send it back. Yellow lined roads for the visually impaired ends in one place. Suddenly an electric pole in front of you. The head hits the sign suddenly. Now there are talking walking sticks. It warns you when you get something out of you. Maybe we could move independently if we got them. For example, my neighbor takes out the garbage bin on the side of the house. How many times I bumped. These are very dangerous." (K2)

"As a visually impaired, on our roads, on the sidewalks you have to be brave to walk. Previously I went out to settle a job in the municipality; I fell into a water-filled pit and broke my foot. And that pit is still open. My daughter comes in the evening and says lets walk, but I'm not going out." (K6)

“I’m having a lot of trouble. It’s impossible to walk on the sidewalk, so I’ve been walking on the roads and once hit by a car. But I still keep walking. I have no other choice.” (K14)

“I’m not going out unless I have to. I can’t go out alone. I used to take a walk with my son. We couldn’t get off the sidewalk from car parks. We had to get on the road. On Sunday, everyone park their cars on the sidewalk. We could not walk.” (K9)

“There are pits everywhere. I’ve already fallen into the pits. There were special walkways for the visually impaired but suddenly ends. Also the transportation can be free to us at least.” (K16)

“I’m afraid of falling into pits. I’m not going out without someone.” (K17)

“Our independence is restricted due to insufficient order.” (K18)

“I manage to see very little at the moment, but soon I will lose my other eye. And I’m so scared. There is no necessary infrastructure for someone who does not see.” (K21)

“Cars are parked on the sidewalks. This time I have to walk on the roads. I’ve been in danger of being hit many times. While walking on the sidewalks again, I hit the obstacles coming in front of me many times. One time I hit my head pretty badly, and I had to get stitches.” (K24)

“I’m having trouble. There are pits everywhere. The sidewalks aren’t smooth. How many times I fall and I got hurt. I’m afraid to go out. There are elevators and traffic lights abroad. There are even separate alphabetical elevators for the visually impaired. It’s impossible to go outside without someone here. If you are there, you will be given an environment to be independent.” (K27)

Table 27: Distribution of public areas according to qualification of public buildings and regulations

Public Places	Sufficient		Insufficient		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Roads	5	16.7	25	83.3	30	100.0
Sidewalks	2	6.7	28	93.3	30	100.0
Stairs	5	16.7	25	83.3	30	100.0
Interchange	1	3.3	29	96.7	30	100.0
Lifts	4	33.3	26	86.7	30	100.0
Toilets	7	23.3	23	76.7	30	100.0
Plan of urban spaces	1	3.3	29	96.7	30	100.0
Transportation Vehicles	1	3.3	29	96.7	30	100.0

Of the visually impaired individuals, 83.3% (25 persons) stated that the roads in the TRNC were insufficient, also 93.3% (28 people) that the sidewalks are insufficient for

visually impaired individuals, 83.3% (25 people) staircase standards are insufficient for a visually impaired person, 96.7% (29 people) that the overpasses are inadequate, 86.7% (26 people) that the elevators are insufficient, 76.7% said that the toilets were inadequate, 96.7% (29 people) stated that both urban spaces and transportation vehicles were insufficient for a visually impaired.

Almost all of the visually impaired individuals who participated in the study stated that roads, sidewalks, stairs, overpasses, elevators, urban space plans and transportation vehicles were insufficient.

Table 28: The emotions of visually impaired individuals when they encounter physical obstacles

Emotions	N	%
Stress	13	17.3
Anger	21	28.0
Sadness	18	24.0
I feel blocked	18	24.0
I don't feel anything	5	6.7
Total	75*	100.0

* More than one answer.

As seen in Table 28, 17.3% of the visually impaired individuals (13 people) experience stress when they face physical disabilities, 28% (21 persons) feel anger, 24% (18 people) feel 24% (18 people feel blocked. Some participants experience all these emotions together when they encounter any physical obstacle in the structures and arrangements of public spaces in their daily life, while some may feel only a single emotion 6.7 %.

In general, about 3/1 of the visually impaired individuals who have participated in the research have problems with the obstacles on the sidewalks.

Apart from these, the stairs do not have a standard size for a visually impaired person, the lack of elevators of the visually impaired individuals who do not want to use the stairs and the absence of any signaling of the elevators, the steps of several interchanges for the visually impaired individuals who want to use the interchange while crossing the street. Lack of toilets that visually impaired individuals, the inadequacy of the means of transportation may prevent the visually impaired individuals from living independently. Visually impaired individuals who experience such physical barriers can feel stress, anger, sadness and disability. It was observed that more than 3/2 of the visually impaired individuals experienced these feelings

It can be said that visually impaired individuals experience an exclusion in the physical environment. In the table below, the exclusion of the visually impaired individuals from the psychosocial perspective will be discussed.

3.3. Findings Related to Social Exclusion Status of Psychosocial Perspectives of Visually Impaired Individuals

Table 29: The status of visually impaired individuals in media tools

The status of visually impaired individuals in media tools	Yes		No		Neutral		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
I think it's handled painfully	21	70.0	2	6.7	7	23.3	30	100.0
I see that the individual is based on his / her disability rather than his / her personal characteristics.	19	63.3	4	13.3	7	23.3	30	100.0
I see it is being projected as individuals in need of help	19	63.3	4	13.3	7	23.3	30	100.0
I think they are used to increase the rating	20	66.7	3	10.0	7	23.3	30	100.0

In Table 29, there are 4 categories in order to learn how individuals with disabilities are reflected in the media of visually impaired individuals and what the visually impaired individuals think about this situation. These categories are; it's handled painfully, the individual is based on his / her disability rather than his / her personal characteristics, it is being projected as individuals in need of help, and the used to increase the rating 70% (21 people) of the 30 disabled individuals in the study think that the visually impaired person is considered to be pitiless in the media. 63.3% (19 people) think that media is based on the disability of the individual instead of personal characteristics, 63.3% (19 people) were reflected in the needy, 66.7% (20 people) think they are used to increase the rating. 23.3% of the participants (7 people) did not give any opinion on these issues. They were hesitant to talk about these issues.

In the following tables, the opinions of the society and the visually impaired person in terms of disability will be discussed and their exclusion will be discussed.

Table 30: Distribution of the society according to the vision of visually impaired people

Theme	Subcodes	f
Perspective	Distrust	3
	Pity	10
	Exclusion	7
	Helper	3
	Disrespectful	5
	Mock	3
	Ignoring	2
	Insensible	3
	No idea	3

The attitudes of the society for visually impaired individuals who participated in the study indicated that 10 people were treated with pity. This point of view supports the handling of visual impairment in the media. 3 people have a distrust of visually impaired individuals, 7 people are reflected that as exclusion, 3 people as a helper society while 3 people are trying to help draw attention to the unconsciousness of the community.

“They look like we can't do anything. They are not trust us.” (K1)

"There's a sense of pity. And there's a feeling of insecurity. Still better than before. 40 years ago, it was a dream for a visually impaired to marry. I lost the girl I loved when I became visually impaired. I loved again, but her parents didn't let me because I was blind. Now that my wife is married to me, she chooses me and her parents didn't. We just made up for it again. Our people are more enlightened now. But still, no one's parent wants her daughter or son marries with a disabled man or woman." (K2)

"Not at all good perspectives. They pity us, they reject." (K3)

"...have an ignorant viewpoint." (K4)

"...there's a sense of pity. I don't want them to pity me." (K6)

"They help. But of course I have to tell myself. They don't help if I don't say." (K8)

"I'm trying not to interfere with society. I'm disturbed by the careful looks. I'm uncomfortable with questions." (K10)

"They look as we are miserable." (K12)

"There is a feeling of pity." (K13)

"There is a sense of pity. Sometimes I took my prosthesis off. It's painful to get used to. When I am not wearing my prosthesis, there are those who afraid and speakers behind me." (K21)

"...unfortunately, very bad. My wife and I go together to vote on every election. Since I'm visually impaired, we'll enter the cabin together. My wife helps me and I use my vote that way. However, in the June 24, 2018 municipal elections, she told the situation to the polling chairman but he said I cannot vote. For the first time in my 40-year marriage, I was subjected to such behavior. I felt so bad and helpless. Despite all the statements we made, I was told to throw my vote in the trunk empty. I rejected it and left." (K24)

"There is unconsciousness. There are many people who do not know how to act to a visually impaired person. This type of training should be given to the community starting from school." (K25)

While 5 people described the point of view of society as disrespect, 3 people were mocked and 2 people were ignored. 3 people did not want to give their opinion on the subject.

"They're shutting me out. There is no helper. They're teasing." (K11)

“The situation changed in the last 3-5 years. They understand that we have merit as any individual. But in some environments we are ignored.” (K15)

“They exclude. They pretend like we don't exist. I try not to get on me, but sometimes it's too tiring to live in a society like this.” (K27)

“They pity and exclude. I'm having a hard time making friends. I feel alone.” (K29)

In the tables below, the exclusion from society will be continued in more detail.

Table 31: The distribution of point of view for visually impaired individuals in the society

The Status of the Disabled in the Society	Yes		No		Sometimes		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
I am exposed negative attitude, behavior	9	30.0	13	43.3	8	26.7	30	100.0
I'm making more effort in relationships	18	60.0	12	40.0	0	0.0	30	100.0
My disability generalized to other areas	7	23.3	17	56.7	6	20.0	30	100.0
Feeling worthless	7	23.3	17	56.7	6	20.0	30	100.0
I want to hide my disability	7	23.3	18	60.0	5	16.7	30	100.0

In Table 31, 5 categories were determined in order to learn the status of visually impaired individuals in society. According to these categories, 30% (9 people) are exposed to negative attitudes and 26.7% are sometimes exposed to these attitudes and behaviors. In total, 56.7% are exposed to negative attitudes and behaviors. 60% of them are making more efforts in relations. 43.3% (13 persons) think that the disability is generalized or generalized to other areas sometimes. Again in the same way, 43.3% may feel or feel worthless due to visual impairment. 40% (12 persons) want to hide the disability or want to hide sometimes.

Table 32: Distribution of visually impaired individuals according to their expectations from society and authorities

Theme	Subcodes	f
Expectations from the Community and Authorities	Education	2
	Ignoring	2
	Priority	3
	Equality	7
	Interest	13
	Employment	3
	Salary	4
	Living space for disabled	9
	No expectations	2

Finally, in Table 32, there was interest in the expectations of 30 visually impaired individuals who participated in the study in terms of expectations from the society and the authorities. 18 people stated that there should be more interest and relevance, not to be ignored, and to give priority to the visually impaired individuals from time to time. 7

people stated that they should be accepted as they are about equality and they want to behave equally as other non-disabled individuals.

4 people stated that the salary of the disabled is inadequate to live as an independent individual, and that 3 people said that employment quota should be opened and 2 people stated that education should increase for visually impaired individuals.

9 people stated that there is a lack of a barrier-free living area and that the visually impaired person is restricted. 2 people have said that there is no expectation.

"...to increase the training and education for the visually impaired. Right now, training for us is not enough. We currently only have 2 teachers." (K1)

"...at least we want them to accept us as we are. We want some priorities to be recognized. Like parking places. For example, people parked their cars more than disabled people. Or they have to help us in hospitals and banks. Right of leading must be given." (K2)

"Some more attention need to be paid, the slogan is that everyone is a candidate for a disabled should at least they must think about it and be more sensitive. There is no interest in the authorities. Nobody asks what you do as a business. I did not get any help from the association, no interest. I lost my eye in the military. But I'm more alive than anyone who sees here. At least we must have a privilege. We have a separate section, if the state says so, should also provide that privilege. (K4)

"Let us be treated equally. The authorities have ignorance. There was never one who asked us. They didn't make a phone call for once. There's no one asking if I'm dead. I enrolled in a blindfolded association 20 years ago. They didn't call once. Where will they know if I die or live?" (K6)

"...salaries too inadequate. We don't even get half the paycheck. I often use taxi for transportation. Not even enough for it. Employment does not open. It hasn't been open in 10 years. I don't get a job for 2,000 Turkish Liras. I Already taking 1400 Turkish Liras." (K8)

"We want respect from society. In addition, the visually impaired should have privileges. We come to mind before only elections." (K9)

"The association is like a family business. I haven't seen any help. They didn't even help me for my salary, and they told me they would kick me out of the association because I didn't pay my dues. My salary is hard enough for me. They're just looking to fill their pockets." (K10)

"We want a layout as visually impaired. We want to live independently." (K12)

"I want to be treated like a normal individual. I want equality. Don't let the disability to go in front of me." (K14)

"Society should be considered us as part of any individual." (K15)

"Disabled associations and authorities are seeking to obtain rant. The approach should be human-scale." (K18)

"We are remembered in a single week of disabled people. Education for the visually impaired needs to be increased." (K19)

"No employment for 10 years. I want staff to open up for us." (K20)

"There is a lack of interest. We're ignored. They must remember that we are a part of society." (K21)

"My expectation from society is respect. In general, there should be more interest, the authorities remember us in a single week of disabled people." (K22)

"There must be appropriate social areas. I want to go to a place like every other person and get together with people. The absence of this is not mine fault, but the society and the authorities." (K27)

"Waiting for your attention and respect. For us, a barrier-free living area should be offered. Nurse and officers should show necessary attention and respect to us." (K28)

"Society should be more sensitive. For example, at least they should not park on the sidewalk. The authorities need to do more. It's not my fault if I am at home all the time like a prisoner at this young age." (K29)

4. Conclusion and Discussion

4.1 Results Regarding Participants' Personal and Disability Level Related Characteristics

According to the data obtained from the questions about this section; most of the participants were male. Most of the female participants did not accept the interview and were seen as shy. Most of the participants were between the ages of 61-70, followed by the 18-30 age groups. They were born in Nicosia and Famagusta; they were married and had children.

It was determined that most of the participants were participants with low vision and no vehicle support. Although participants requested vehicle support (white walking stick), they stated that this support was not provided by the association. Some

participants have not been able to benefit from the help or even don't know about some of the benefits. Accordingly, it could be said that the use of vehicle support could be more if the support provided by the association.

Visually impaired people who have participated in the study have had disability after birth. They have been visually impaired in the 7-15 age group due to consanguineous marriages, birth in bad conditions during delivery and accidents after birth.

4.2 Corporate and Economic Social Exclusion Status Results for Visually Impaired Individuals

In this section, data on the exclusion of visually impaired individuals in the areas of employment, education, health and physical environment are collected.

According to data on employment, visually impaired individuals are generally retired or unemployed. Only 3 people who can benefit from the disability quota from 30 visually impaired individuals participating in the research. In general, they were able to find a job with their own efforts. Disabled people, negative working conditions, physical work environment negatively affected their working lives. The income of the disabled is insufficient for the basic needs of the household. In general, individuals with disabilities who have participated in the research have either left their jobs or have retired early due to an increase in the level of disability. The absence of equal environment and quota were reflected negatively in the work life.

According to the data collected for the exclusion status of the visually impaired individuals in terms of education, in general, they are secondary school graduates; they go to general education institution instead of special education institutions. There were problems about the absence of educational environment suitable for the visually impaired, in the mockery and exclusion of peers, in peer support, additional assistance, support and financial difficulties within the classroom. Accordingly, visually impaired individuals who do not attend or continue their education after secondary school are predominant.

According to the responses of the visually impaired individuals to the health services, it was concluded that they experienced difficulties in transportation and personal assistance in health services. In addition, there is no satisfaction with the practice in health institutions. It can be said that physical facilities of health institutions are not suitable for visually impaired individuals, and buildings such as stairs and roads inside and outside the building make it difficult for visually impaired individuals. Even visually impaired individuals who went to hospitals to benefit from health services stated that they experienced falls, injuries and bruises. Based on this, it can be said that the buildings in the health sector were designed by excluding the visually impaired or disabled individuals.

There are visually impaired individuals who lose their eye completely or partially because of the wrong treatment, and there are also visually impaired individuals who have medication problems. While providing medication, they stated

that disabled salary was not enough, problems were experienced or drugs were not available in the market and that the treatment was delayed. It is stated that the operations performed in the TRNC are troublesome, and that the operations abroad do not meet their own financial powers if the board does not meet the material. It is also stated that there is no psychological support after operations in TRNC. Visually impaired individuals who are not able to see again without psychological support can enter into a great depression. For these reasons, it can be said that visually impaired individuals face unconsciousness and apathy in the health sector.

It was concluded that the visually impaired individuals had difficulty in independence according to their responses in terms of social exclusion in the physical environment. There are certain obstacles that prevent the independence, some of them are not a layout of sidewalks, they can be injured by the obstacles in front of them constantly on the sidewalks, such as putting the signboard as they wish, putting garbage can or using the pavements for parking their cars, visually impaired individuals who cannot walk on the sidewalks are forced to walk to the pits. the risk of crashing, the danger of a car crash, the lack of signaling or not working properly may cause accidents, the yellow lined roads are not in compliance with the standards or can be terminated without any warning, without the necessary infrastructure and regulations. it can be said that 3/2 of the visually impaired participants independence can become dependent.

Apart from these, the stairs need to have standard dimensions for a visually impaired person, while there is no half of the stairs or the broken ones, the lack of elevators and the absence of any signaling or braille alphabet of elevators, who do not want to use the stairs, want to use the overpasses, the steps of several lower-overpasses are very spaced, the design and insufficiency, Inadequacy of the toilets which can be used by visually impaired individuals who prefer to leave the house less, and the insufficiency of the means of transportation can be problematic for visually impaired individuals.

Although the municipality in Nicosia was a means of transportation for disabled people, it was seen that they did not benefit enough. Disabled individuals who use this means of transport to handle their work are left alone. In other provinces, there is not even any means of transportation provided by the municipality. Visually impaired individuals who experience such physical barriers can feel stress, anger, sadness and disability. It was observed that more than 3/2 of the visually impaired individuals experienced these feelings. According to these points, visually impaired individuals are highly excluded in the physical environment.

4.3 The Results of Psychosocial Social Exclusion Status of Visually Impaired Individuals

In this section, the social exclusion of the visually impaired individuals participating in the research will be discussed.

According to the data collected, visually impaired individuals in the media shown as different adjectives (poor, other, need help, etc.) instead of revealing the personal characteristics of disability. In addition, the visually impaired individuals interviewed think that the time they find in the media is only on the special days of the week of the disability or the locals. They stated that their own space was not in the media and was ignored.

According to the questions about society, the visually impaired individuals stated that the perspective of the group was viewed with pity. This point of view supports the handling of visual impairment in the media. They stated that there was a distrust towards visually impaired individuals, that there was exclusion, they were drawing attention to the unconsciousness of the society. Visually impaired individuals may be subject to negative attitudes and behaviors by the society.

The person who makes more effort for social relations can be visually impaired. They can be forced and excluded when acquiring friends or acquiring social relations. It may be said that they had been ignoring from time to time and are far away from the need to be seen by the public and the authorities. They are faced with pity and exclusion by the community. This shows that this situation is consistent with the situation reflected by the media in the previous chapter. From time to time it can be said that the disability is not seen as an equal and normal individual. Again, this situation is consistent with the state of the visually impaired in previous with the media.

Officials remember the visually impaired individuals only on the special days of the disabled or the disabled. This situation has been interpreted by the visually impaired individuals as providing benefit and rent. The Association was also very uninterested and said that they would not even be called once a year. This is consistent with the inability of the researcher to reach an up-to-date list despite interviews with the association.

In addition, some visually impaired individuals have access to vehicle support and assistance provided by the association and some visually impaired people cannot reach these aids.

In order to determine the dimensions of Social Exclusion through the Corporate, Economic and Psychosocial Aspects of Visually Impaired Individuals, 30 visually impaired individuals were interviewed to determine some important problems in terms of their exclusion.

When the research findings were examined, it was determined that most of the participants were male. Most of the female participants did not accept the interview and were seen as shy. This is consistent with other studies (Ergüden, 2008; Özdemir, 2012).

According to the findings in terms of employment, visually impaired individuals; disability, negative working conditions, physical work environment adversely affected working life. It can be said that it is insufficient for visually impaired individuals who try to get on a disabled salary. In general, the disabled individuals who participated in the research have quit because of the increase in the level of disability. The absence of equal environment and quota were reflected negatively in the work life.

The results of the data collected from the perspective of employment support the researches on this subject (Baykoc, 2014; Dernekbas, 2010; Genç, 2015; Ergüden, 2008)

In terms of education, it was experienced difficulties in transportation to the educational institution, physical arrangements of buildings and in-house structures and regulations, lack of educational environment suitable for the visually impaired, mockery and exclusion by his peers, peer support, additional assistance, support and financial difficulties. The results of the data gathered from the point of research education support the studies carried out in this respect. (Watch, 2013; Tobias & Mukhopadhyay 2017; Öztürk, 2011; Akbulut, 2012)

In the health sector, visually impaired individuals may experience problems about transportation and personal assistance, in examinations, in the physical formation of health institutions, and the visually impaired individuals face unconsciousness and apathy. The results of the research in the health sector have shown consistency with previous researches. (Dauti, 2015; Gerben, Susan, Phillip, Gwyn, Thilo, & Melinda, 2002; Kördeve, 2017)

In terms of social exclusion in the physical environment, they may experience stress, anger, sadness and frustration when they experience difficulties in independence and experience these difficulties. Visually impaired individuals can be highly excluded and feel excluded from the physical environment. The results of the study are consistent with the researches on this subject. (Rimer & others, 2004; Yılmaz, 2005; Ozturk, 2011; Kordeve, 2017)

According to the findings in terms of media, visually impaired individuals stated that they are excluded in the media; the medical model of the disability can be said to enable the disabled individuals to be handled in this way in the media. Researches also supports this (Ralston & Ho, 2010; Fahnestock, 2011) Considering that the media has a major role in shaping the thoughts of the society (Hardin & Hardin 2001; Ralston & Ho, 2010; Fahnestock, 2011), it is thought that the opinions of the society can be reflected with the adjectives such as disabled, poor, helpless and ignored individuals.

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